

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS IN THE LESSONS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Mizayeva Laylo

Termiz State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379216>

Annotation: This article discusses about the development of skills in the lessons of foreign languages and given some important information

Keywords: skills, lesson-seminar, a lesson conference, development of cognitive

The use of innovate technologies in lessons has great advantages. The learning process becomes interesting for students, which increases the activity of students, develops skills to independently acquire knowledge in the process of interaction and search. Improves the quality and strength of the knowledge gained. Developing research skills and abilities, forming analytical abilities of students. In parallel with the learning process, there is a development of communicative qualities and the formation of leadership qualities of the individual. The development of cognitive activity is promoted and non-traditional lessons that allow to increase the student's interest in the subject and to learning in general. There are several classifications of non-standard lessons and many of their types: lesson-seminar, lesson-lecture, lesson-conversation, lesson-practice, lesson excursion, lesson-study, lesson-game, lesson-KVN, lesson-defense of the project, lesson-dispute , a lesson conference, a lesson-theatrical performance, a masquerade lesson, a lesson-journey, a lesson-set-off. Almost all of them allow you to ask problematic questions and create problem situations, solve the problems of differentiated training, activate educational activities, increase cognitive interest, and contribute to the development of critical thinking. Non-traditional lessons of the Russian language and literature provide a systematic analysis of linguistic information, develop language observance. That's why I apply all the above kinds of lessons with pleasure in my work. It is estimated that on average the student speaks for 3-5 minutes during five lessons. I think that the teachers will not be surprised by this data, but, no doubt, they will make you think about the problem. Therefore, today lessons are relevant - debates, discussions. A large part of the work in preparing for this lesson falls on the shoulders of the teacher: choosing a topic, approaching the problem, drawing up a discussion plan, selecting questions.

This form of work is more effective in literature lessons. With all the diversity and effectiveness of non-traditional lessons, it is often impossible to use them for a variety of reasons. But in fact so it would be desirable, that each lesson was especial, with the "highlight". Therefore, we can resort to non-standard, creative elements of a separate traditional lesson. This can be either a lexical dictation or a dictation-crossword, and puzzle-making in a lesson, and a commented letter or warning dictations with a "tractor driver". Another effective tool is didactic games that can provoke interest in learning Russian. The aim of the game is to arouse interest in knowledge, science, books, and teachings. Along with the teaching takes an important place in the development of the child. When children are included in the situation of a didactic game, the interest in learning activity increases sharply, the

material being studied becomes more accessible to them, the work capacity is significantly increased.

An important role of entertaining didactic games is also in the fact that they help to relieve tension in children, creates a positive emotional mood during the lesson. I use a large number of didactic linguistic games: this and the task of "Eliminate excess", "Learn me", "Virtual reference bureau" and others that instill the ability to synthesize and comprehend information.

The main thing is that there is no time for the children to be bored at the lesson so that they would like to work and study, and in this case the success situation, which, as a rule, is created by non-standard lessons or elements of lessons, and the independence to which the children are accustomed in such lessons, and creative attitude to the native language, which is brought up only on creative lessons. Types of homework:

- creative work;
- preparation of illustrations for literary works, creation of presentation on literary works;
- drawing of covers, filmstrips to literary works;
- artistic reading; - a dramatization of a work of art;
- historical commentary to the works (slideshow);
- creation of independent literary works of various genres;
- the continuation of unfinished works;
- observation of nature (photo and video);
- preparation of dictionary dictations;
- preparation of the questionnaire for offset by topic;
- drawing up a summary, supporting tables;
- presentation (review of the heroes of the work, biography of the writer); a letter from memory. Such homework helps to avoid monotony, routine in training. The child can feel himself in the role of the author, both as an illustrator and as a teacher. Unusual tasks activate thinking, make the child generalize, systematize the material on the topic. Innovative methods of teaching in the school contribute to the development of cognitive interest in children, they teach to systematize and generalize the studied material, discuss and discuss. Comprehending and processing the acquired knowledge, students acquire the skills of applying them in practice, gaining experience of communication.

Undoubtedly, innovative methods of teaching have advantages over traditional ones, because they contribute to the development of the child, teach him independence in cognition and decision-making. It is interesting for pupils to act, actively participate in the course of the lesson, make mistakes and look for the causes of mistakes, formulate questions, and not just answer them, ie. they want to take an active communicative position in the classroom. The teacher's task is to help the student to see his role in the lesson, to translate the schoolchild's educational activity into a creative plane. I think there is no point in proving that the use of new technologies at different stages of the lesson helps to make it effective, effective, and the process of obtaining knowledge for students is interesting and productive.

Bibliography:

1. Crystal D. Language and the Internet.–Cambridge:Cambridge University Press, 2001.– 272 p.

2. Larsen-Freeman, D. Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching [Text] / D. Larsen-Freeman. – Oxford University Press, 2007. – 191 p.
3. Derevyashkina N.M. Informational technologies in science and education /Irkutsk, 2007.- 51p.
4. Shelehova O.V. Formation of students'project abilities while usage computer technologies/ Irkutsk, 2004.- 178p.